

ISSUES OF ANTHROPONYMY IN UZBEK AND RUSSIAN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. *In the article, anthroponyms have a certain place in the Uzbek and Russian languages. They are also characterized by the presence of indicators unique to it. Also, anthroponyms are distinguished from other lexical compounds by semantic, stylistic and compositional features. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out onomastic research on the basis of a systematic structural and historical-comparative method in a synchronous and diachronic plan. Names also inform about the generation of a certain person, his place in society.*

Keywords: *anthroponym, indicators, onomastic, semantic, identification, linguocultural.*

The study of anthroponyms is a long-standing tradition in domestic and foreign linguistics. Over the past years, research has been carried out in five main areas: general theory of names; history of Russian anthroponyms; current state of Russian anthroponymy; anthroponyms in fiction; practical questions of anthroponymy. This research examines the current state of Russian anthroponymy, the history of Russian anthroponyms, as well as issues of teaching methodology. The main distinguishing features of a proper name are as follows:

1) it is given to a separate object and not to a class of objects that are characteristic of all individuals of this class;

2) the object named using its own name is always clearly defined, limited, limited;

3) the name is not directly related to the concept and does not have a clear and unambiguous meaning at the language level. These features, even if the boundary between proper and common nouns seems to be blurred and unclear, make words allow to be classified as an appellative. At the current stage, from the linguistic point of view, personal nouns form a subsystem in the language system according to their semantic, phonetic and morphological characteristics. A language chooses what fits its models and trends. Not all nouns are equally known to people who speak a certain language: there are words that are actively used and words that belong to the passive reserve. In the case of proper names, compared to common nouns, the passive fund is many times larger than the active one, and therefore the question arises about the level of their entry into the language and the limits of the actual composition of the language. At one point, the name change became a legal issue. Personal names, as an integral part of the history and culture of any people, try to preserve their national identity in any language environment, therefore even today personal names are not translated, they are transmitted by transcription.

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Subjective adverbs in personal nouns have an emotional-evaluative feature, and the emotional value in them comes to the fore and clearly dominates. The direct purpose of subjective adverbs is a new 'z is not to create, but to change an existing word by introducing an emotional-modal shade into it, to show the subject's personal relationship to the person called, i.e. these word forms. Primary subjective evaluation forms are formed by adding forming morphemes to the full noun (Petr-Petrusha) or to separate syllables (Anna-Anya). 2nd evaluation line is output. Additions are added to them and the 3rd row is obtained (Peter - Parsley - Parsley). This is an additional method of creating emotional-evaluative forms (Mitrofanova, 1958, 125) Sometimes it can be a selection of syllables from a full or diminutive noun without adding formative elements - the real form of "subjective evaluation" abbreviation: Valentina - Tina; Alexander - Sasha - Sashura

- Shura (4th row and cutting); Boris - Borussia - Busya (3rd row and cut). Only 5 lines. In fact - there are not many truncated forms, and it is worth noting that they often resemble stems that can be called "bound", since only one sound remains from the full name, followed by a subjective evaluation suffix comes, is taken as a final vowel. Formative Suffix (Sho'ra). In personal nouns, the method of forming the suffix is dominant. If the forming stem ends or begins with a consonant, morphemes consisting of or beginning with vowels are added (- a, - I, - kulak, - point, - onka, - kulak, - happy, - unya, - uta

- ik and - ka). If the forming stem ends with a vowel, then suffixes starting with a consonant (-sha, -nya, -ha) are added. - yes, gives names a "final" design, ie. suffixes cannot be added or cut. - sha, - nya, - kulak, - unya, - hurray, - uta and affixes - make intermediate character forms. In addition to specific changes in the formation of personal names, the general order morphological processes occur. For example, complex adverbs are formed on the basis of simple adverbs - ush + -ka, -ur + -ka. There are several groups of nouns, depending on the nature of the relations / feelings, evaluations accompanying the address to the interlocutor:

1) informal - neutral names are common, everyday names that do not come with a pronunciation phrase. They convey the intimacy of a relationship. Common forms are nouns with the suffixes - a, - e, and - sha.

- nya, - ka (in the environment of children, youth and youth). If such an appeal applies to adults, then these are familiar - neutral names (Tanya, Sasha, Anya)

2) affectionate names mean affection, love, friendship. They are characterized by the additions - dot, - onka, - ear, less often - urka, - duck (Lenochka, Mishutka, Temochka) 3) moral - derogatory nouns express contempt and neglect, and add - ka (Mashka, Tanya) is formed using the suffix ' . , Dimka)

4) emotional - negative forms represent a temporary expression caused by the speaker's anger.

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